

(Influence of Gender on Career Aspiration among Secondary School Biology ... Junaidu, H. I., Et. al. 2025)

Influence of Gender on Career Aspiration among Secondary School Biology Students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of Gender on career aspiration among secondary school Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study employed the descriptive research design method which was guided by two research questions and one null hypothesis. The sample for the study was 260 respondents which consisted of senior secondary school II students' which were randomly selected from 15 public secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria Educational Zone. Data were obtained from using the Career Aspiration of Biology Students Questionnaire (CABSQ) with a reliability coefficient of 0.92 and the inferential statistics (t- test) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that gender has no significant influence on the career aspirations among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State; Based on the findings, it was recommended that Secondary school students should be encouraged from time to time to visit the counselling unit whenever the need arises, students should be acquainted with this services so that they can be properly guided on their academics and career aspirations and preferences and parents should assist their adolescent with career-related decision making. This may help them understand their child's perspectives and career needs, provide appropriate support and encouragement, and enhance the natural alliance that exists between them and the child.

Keywords: Career, Career Aspirations, Career Choice, Gender

Introduction

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The activities performed by biologist, play a major role of exposing biological careers to students in various areas of life. The term career opportunity can be defined as an occupation chosen as one's life work. The talk about career and career choices begins right from the home, where children even at very early stage in life begin to show preference for certain careers. To some extent, parents affect the decisions their children make about such choices. The term aspiration, on the other hand has been defined by Lewin (1951) as the process of choosing the goals within the field". He further explains the importance of aspiration to life as something that provide a number of sought after links with the investment required in achieving something including identification of the personal internal value, and the measuring of individual differences. In general, the ambition to achieve as well as measures of achievement of cognitive created status may condition career aspiration. Careers in biology can be those that involve the use of scientific tools and techniques to study living things in researchers, health care, Environment management and conservation, education, Zoo, and historical centres (Bongard & Levin, 2021). Biologist may also be writers of biological books, journals, articles, fliers and magazines. They may also be involved in the collection and preservation of specimens in laboratories, Zoos and museums important in providing historical career biology to novel learners (Rees, 2023).

Gaburro and Rieux (2024) reported that career knowledge and information in the life science is needed in all areas such as government, business, private and academic sectors. Students with biology career can choose occupation biology career can choose occupation elsewhere in the related filed like business, politics and policy, industries, forensic science, economics, science writing and communication and art (Harrison, 2023). However, some students make choice according to their current feelings, interest ability and influence from their parents, family and peers. Yu (2023) assumes that students performing complicated tasks require possession of requisite mastery skills and work reflected in personal efficiencies that enable the translation of skills into a productive performance.

The aim of biological secondary education is to impart knowledge, skills and provide information that would enable students to manage different tasks pertaining to all forms of life (Musaxonovna, 2022). It orients specific qualities, fits in the operations of related careers. Lent et al. According to Jiang et al., (2024) career aspirations and choice behaviours is shaped by ones' self-efficacy, interest, outcomes and expectations. All of these, self- efficacy plays a mediating role between one's background (context), learning environments (inputs) and performing tasks (process). They also, pointed at other factors that are important in shaping career aspirations. These included family background, individual's variants such as gender health status, and ethnicity, cognitive variables and learning experiences. Upon the specific kinds of occupation and during the increase in understanding, students may develop their aspirations for selecting related careers after graduating (Quinlan & Renninger, 2022).

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Sellami et al., (2023) stated that, in order to enhance students' career aspirations in secondary schools, when relating the level of education, knowledge and skills, beliefs, interests, attitudes, perceptions and values towards the subject have to be related to his careers. Zhang et al., (2023) emphasizes that there are new careers being added to the world of work, which need attention. Thus, through learning biological sciences, the younger generation will raise awareness of various career paths and opportunities, which would lead them to overcome the challenges they face in career choices. The psychological concept of self-efficacy could be used in many aspects of biological sciences in secondary education that can be related to students' career aspirations. Karaca-Atik, (2023) investigated various important aspects in the study of career aspiration. These included individuals' ability, background, and life styles. However, Tandrayen-Ragoobur and Gokulsing (2022) added socio-economic levels, learning process and gender roles as other external variables important in understanding individual's career aspirations.

Abina et al., (2025) pointed out several steps students have to follow when choosing careers which include; self-assessment, evaluation of careers, consultation of expertise, diversification of opportunities, and having a list of possible careers. According to Quinlan and Renninger (2022) students with good academic performance in genetics chose biology subject as their career path for further studies. It was considered that a good performance in genetics topic implied the possession of biological skills was valued as a success entrance into biological occupations such as genetic engineering, agricultural and livestock production. Cheng et al., (2021) reported that, most students studying biology chose medicine as their preferred career for their future. They were able to understand and value that biology subject provided the knowledge and skills required in such career.

Generally, males and females think differently towards the nature of subjects something, which reflects differences in career aspirations. Williams (2023) argued that unequal access in education causes few women to occupy professional occupations than men. However, the government have been making efforts to reduce education discrimination which is also manifested in the career choices. Thus, men and women have equal chances of choosing any professional careers like aspiring to become medical doctor and engineers. Mengba(2022) asserted that traditionally, in many African societies, the differences between the two groups are caused by social role and expectations orienting males and females to stereotyping activities. Males are supposed to provide the principal economic support of the family. They can effectively execute these roles by being exposed to a variety of occupations from which they can make choices. Culturally girls are the wives and mothers exposed to a very few occupations for choices.

Rudman (2021) further states that, the specifications of the relationship of beliefs and attitudes commonly assumed associated with gender roles; influence the feelings and

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expectations between female and males in selection of the work. In career choices, females have been found to be more affected with restrictions which deny them the right of choosing certain career. Females were found to have low self-confidences in sciences and they believed that they are less able in science subjects (Siani & Harris, 2023). These beliefs affect many girls by making them not choose sciences as their career paths and not thinking about science related careers, with biological careers being among them (Rosenzweig & Chen, 2023). This is in line with beliefs held by many people in the society particularly parents and teachers.

Wrigley-Asante et al., (2022) found that females achieving better in the subject had high aspiration for science subject related matters than male do because they were confident, had high expectation and valued it. This suggests that, students' sex and their expected occupations are associated with their parents' attitudes, positivist role models, the future labour force, feminist attitude, self-efficacy, cultural beliefs and environmental sport (Nderitu, 2024). Furthermore, Gati and Kulcsár (2021) viewed that, careers that students expect to have in the related fields seem to be predictive for the career choices that they make later on. For example, female students in the secondary schools who study biology are far more likely than males to report expected occupations related to life sciences and health, including biology, pharmacy, medicine and medical assistance, dentistry, nutrition and nursing, as well as professions related to teaching (Ventura 1992; & Ngezi (Riegle-Crumb & Peng, 2021). These findings reflect that women dominate some biological the careers than men, which ensured the differences in career aspirations. Therefore, this study assessed career aspirations of male and female biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Career aspirations are important in shaping students' educational careers and future occupational choices. In the realm of science education, particularly biology, these aspirations are influenced by a confluence of personal interests, socio-cultural norms, gender roles, and access to career information (Fulani, Amole, & Adeboye, 2020). In Nigeria, persistent gender disparities in science-related career aspirations are often attributed to societal stereotypes, parental expectations, and cultural norms (Madu, 2020). Despite initiatives aimed at promoting gender equity in science education, disparities remain evident in the career paths pursued by male and female students (Wrigley-Asante, 2022). Concerns have emerged regarding the alignment of male and female biology students' career aspirations with their academic potential and the nation's developmental needs. Studies suggest that gender-based perceptions, limited career guidance, and a scarcity of role models in scientific fields may influence students' aspirations, potentially limiting diversity and inclusion in science-related careers (Iloakasia, 2021; Ohimege, Muhammed, &

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Danja, 2021). However, there is a paucity of empirical data examining the extent of gender differences in career aspirations among biology students and the underlying factors contributing to these differences. Therefore, this study investigates the career aspirations of male and female biology students in senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to find out the influence of Gender on career aspiration among secondary school Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. To realize this purpose, the study specifically sought to:

1. Determine the factor responsible for students' choices of career in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria.
2. Explore the gender differences on career aspirations among Biology students.

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions:

1. What are the factors responsible for students' career decisions in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?
2. What are the career aspirations of Biology students on the basis of gender in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho: Gender has no significant influence on the career aspirations of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state.

Methodology

The study examines career aspirations of biology students in secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. The nature of the study is quantitative, hence a descriptive research design that was comparative in nature was used in this study. The design was seen as suitable in this study because it examined the state of the phenomenon as it exists at the time of the study. The population of this study consists of all the nine hundred and thirty-four (934) male and female public senior secondary school two (SSS II) students in the eleven (11) senior secondary schools within

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Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria education zone, Kaduna State. The rationale for choosing senior secondary school II (SSS II) students is that they are offering the subject biology and should be able to give the required information for the study. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select two hundred and sixty (260) respondents at random from the eleven (11) public senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Zaria Educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Data were obtained through the administration of Career Aspiration of Biology Students Questionnaire which was subjected to face and content validation by three experts: one from the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, one from the Department of Science Education and one from the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, all in Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria. These experts scrutinized the instrument in terms of: clarity of instruction to the subject, proper wording of the items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items for the study, structure and adequate timing. The input from these experts was used to modify the questionnaire items.

In order to determine and establish the reliability of the instrument. The test-retest reliability method was employed in this study. The instrument was administered twice to the sampled respondent, after two weeks interval. This was to measure the degree of consistency or stability overtime. To determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to calculate the r-value. A Reliability Coefficient of 0.92 was obtained. This indicated that the instrument is reliable.

Data were collected through the administered questionnaires. The distribution of the questionnaire was personally done in the sampled senior secondary schools by the researcher. Copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents and was collected immediately after it was completed. This ensured higher return rate. Secondly, the researcher responded to the respondents' questions in cases of difficulties. All copies of the questionnaire distributed to the students were collected at the spot after responding to them. The data obtained were analyzed using frequency distributions and simple percentages to answer the research questions. Considerable use of tables for presentation and analysis of the data were made. The Inferential statistics (Paired sample t-test) was used to test the null hypotheses at $p < 0.05$ level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What are the factors responsible for students' career decisions in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?

The data generated were analyzed and used to draw Table 1.

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Table 1: Factors Influencing for the Career Decision of Students

Influencing Factors	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Parents Opinion	29	14.22	10	17.86
Aptitude in Related Subjects	06	02.94	04	07.14
Guidance Counsellor	11	05.39	09	16.07
Principal/Teachers	05	02.45	11	19.64
Interest in the Job	17	08.33	06	10.71
Country's Present Needs	15	07.35	02	03.57
Service to others	25	12.25	02	07.14
Low Cost of Training	22	10.78	01	03.57
Prestige in the Job	41	20.11	07	01.79
High Salary	33	16.18	07	12.50
Total	204	100	56	100

Data presented in Table 1, shows the summary of students responses in respect of the influencing factors in their career decisions. In rank order, prestige in the job and high salary had a higher percentage rating with 20.11% and 16.18% respectively. This indicate that students' choice of occupation is more often than not determined by materialistic considerations such as high pay and prestige. Coming next as a factor responsible for the career decisions of students is 'Parent Opinion', scoring 14.22% and aptitude in related subjects at 2.94% being the least rated factor influencing students' career decisions.

Research Question Two: What are the career aspirations of Biology students based on gender in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state, Nigeria?

Table 2: The Influence of Gender in Career Aspirations

Career Aspirations	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Medicine and Surgery	13	10.32	32	23.88
Nursing Science	11	08.73	11	08.21

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Veterinary	15	11.90	19	14.18
Medicine				
Microbiology	05	03.97	08	05.97
Laboratory	12	09.52	04	02.99
Science				
Biological	09	07.15	08	05.97
Science				
Agricultural	04	03.17	02	01.49
Science				
Computer	23	18.25	15	11.19
Science				
Pharmacy	16	12.70	22	16.42
Lecturer/Teacher	18	14.29	13	09.70
Total	126	100	134	100

Data presented in Table 2 shows that the male students' most preferred career aspiration is in computer science with 18.25% response rate, closely followed by career aspirations in teaching/Lecturing and pharmaceutical science at 14.29% and 12.70% response rating respectively. On contrary, their female counterparts indicated a career aspiration in Medicine and Surgery as their most preferred career choice with 23.88% response rate, closely followed by career aspirations in pharmaceutical science and veterinary medicine at 16.42% and 14.18% response rating respectively. While both the male and female participants were unanimous in rating career aspiration in agricultural science 3.17% and 1.49% respectively as their least preferred career choice.

Null Hypothesis: Gender has no significant influence on the career aspirations of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna state.

Table 3: Summary of t-test Analysis on Gender Influence on Students Career Aspirations

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Career Preferences and Gender	260	11.37	16.64	4	1.79	0.89	Retained

Data analyzed in Table 3 revealed that the probability associated with the calculated value oft (1.79) is 0.89. Since the probability value of 0.89 is greater than the 0.05 level of

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significance, the null hypothesis is retained, therefore, gender has no significant influence on the career aspirations of Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna state.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study revealed that, gender has no significant influence on the career aspirations among Biology students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State. From the analysis, it was observed that both the male and female students were equally exposed to adequate career information with an equal societal expectation on career aspirations in Biology and Biology related discipline. Therefore, gender has no significant factor on the career aspirations of Biology students in senior secondary schools. It is in the light of this that, De Mello et al., (2021) observed that special educationists should devote more time and expertise on disability and gender related issues in order to avert any form of gender related discrimination.

Conclusion

This study has identified that career aspirations in the field of Biology is often influence by students' career knowledge and academic achievement in Biology as a subject in senior secondary school. The study concluded that, gender factor has significant influence on the career aspirations of Biology students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Secondary school students should be encouraged from time to time to visit the counselling unit whenever the need arises, students should be acquainted with this services so that they can be properly guided on their academics and career aspirations and preferences.
2. Parents should assist their adolescent with career-related decision making. This may help them understand their child's perspectives and career needs, provide appropriate support and encouragement, and enhance the natural alliance that exists between them and the child.

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